

Deliverable 5.1

REPORT ON DATA ACCESS AND DATA PROCESSING POLICIES AND USER JOURNEY MAPS ACROSS THE ECOSYSTEM

Primary Author(s)	Jan van den Brand, PhD (ERASMUS)
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AUTHORS

LEAD CONTRIBUTOR	Jan van den Brand, Erasmus MC
OTHER CONTRIBUTORS	Pekka Kahri, HUS Gary Liew, GOSH Andrew Taylor, GOSH Cristina Ruiz Herguido, HSJD Arnau Valls Esteve, HSJD Elina Dimina, BKUS Inese Gobina, BKUS Beatrice Casarella, MEYER Max Salmi, VEIL.AI Tomi Mustonen, TietoEvry Antti Kettunen, TietoEvry

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1. Executive Summary

The current document describes current and target procedures for data access of data controllers participating in the PHEMS ecosystem. We describe a robust data access process, aligning with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) framework and adhering to GDPR’s privacy by design and data minimisation principles. This process handles different data types, including pseudonymised, synthetic, and aggregated data.

The most important conclusion is that the PHEMS data access process effectively navigates the complex legal and policy landscape at European, national, and institutional levels. It ensures compliance with all relevant laws, regulations, and ethical guidelines.

Next steps in Work Package 5, Task 5.2 will involve implementing a monitoring and evaluation plan to measure the performance, quality, and impact of the data access process. This plan will use defined indicators, methods, and tools, providing valuable insights for continuous improvement and ensuring the PHEMS project’s ongoing success in improving pediatric healthcare across Europe

2. List of Abbreviations and Definitions

API	Application Programming Interface
BKUS	Children's University Hospital in Riga (Latvia)
DAA	Data Access Agreement
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
EHR	Electronic Health Record
HSJD	Hospital San Juan de Deu (Spain)
HUS	Helsinki University Hospital (Finland)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GOSH	Great Ormond Street Hospital (UK)
OMOP CDM	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model
PHEMS	
PHI	Personal Health Information
SPE	Secure processing environment

3. Introduction

At present, signing of legal documents concerning the transfer and use of data for research with health data take weeks to months to draft, review, and revise before they are approved by all involved parties. Within PHEMS we envision two major types of legal documents concerning data use: a Data Access Agreement (DAA) and a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA). The main difference between the two is where data control reside. A DAA allows a data user to access PHI, either directly or indirectly, and use these data to create derivative, aggregate data. However, the data does not leave control of the data controller and is not transferred to the data user. For example, a data user wants to perform a research project with PHI data. The PHI data may be placed in a secure processing environment (SPE) within the network of a data controller. Then the data user is invited to the SPE to use the data to perform a scientific analysis. The results from the analysis may be downloaded by the data user through an airlocking mechanism after approval of the data controller. Once a project is finished, data access is revoked and the data user can no longer access the SPE. During the entire project, the data controller remained in control of the PHI and the data user only had access to the data, but control over the PHI was never transferred to the data user. Conversely, a DTA allows control over the PHI to be transferred from the data user to the data controller, making the data user a data controller as well. For example, a data user wants to perform a research project with PHI data. The data controller sends a copy of the data via a secure transfer protocol to the data user, who stores the data within their own network. This means that the data user now has control over the PHI. After the end of the project the data user will need to archive or delete the data as detailed in the DTA. As consequence, we envision that a DAA may be more lightweight than a DTA, as the liability and data protection risks to the data controller are lower when only access is given to PHI as opposed to transferring PHI.

Regardless of the method of data use chose chosen, we still believe there are multiple bottlenecks during the drafting of DAAs and DTAs, such as:

- the decision what template to use (e.g. a nationally created one, the one from the data provider, or the one from the data user),
- several rounds of back and forth sending of a draft agreement,
- unclear ownership and responsibilities for obtaining the agreements, and
- low adoption of automation tools to support drafting the agreements.

Moreover, the process tends to be open to variations in interpretation by reviewers of (parts of) an agreement, which means that very similar use cases may end up with different requirements. As a consequence, the current process is hard to reproduce and repeat, time consuming and cumbersome to all involved.

Therefore, the aim of task 5.1 is to design a data access process that is fast to complete, similar to the way End-User License Agreements are used to grant access to software applications. In order to achieve this, contributors detailed scenarios that serve as input for automated policies, operating procedures, and processes for organizations at various

stages of data maturity. Participating organizations were HUS, ERASMUS, HSDJ, and GOSH, with BKUS and MEYER to validate these scenarios as newly onboarded organizations.

Within this task we set out to

- Define use cases for multi-site studies in the PHEMS ecosystem. For each use case define the type of data (e.g., pseudonymized, anonymized, synthetic, aggregated) that is accessible within a context (e.g., local, federated, central) and used for a type of analysis (e.g. local, federated, centralised, meta-analysis)
- Visualize data flow from source to endpoint at each of the participating partner hospitals.
- Map the user journeys (for data users, data controllers, and data providers) and data flows through the different organizations using directed acyclic graphs (DAG) to identify common nodes (process steps) and edges (policy gates), and partner specific exceptions.
- Map partner specific policies, operating procedures and processes onto the DAGs
- Map regulations and legislation (EU and national) onto the DAGs

4. Results

4.1. Use cases

We have identified the following use cases based on the identifiability of the data subject, ordering them from highest data protection risk to lowest.

4.1.1. Directly identifiable personal data

Personal data according to GDPR means that: *data subjects are identifiable if they can be directly or indirectly identified, especially by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or one of several special characteristics, which expresses the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, commercial, cultural or social identity of these natural persons. In practice, these also include all data which are or can be assigned to a person in any kind of way. For example, the telephone, credit card or personnel number of a person, account data, number plate, appearance, customer number or address are all personal data.*(1) In PHEMS we use the term ‘directly identifiable’ personal data to highlight the distinction between pseudonymised personal data at the patient level and personal data at the patient level that does not require additional steps for identification.

4.1.2. Pseudonymized personal data

According to GDPR: *‘pseudonymisation’ means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure that the personal data are*

not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.(1) In PHEMS, we interpreted this to mean personal data that does not directly identify an individual and can only be traced to an individual's identity by someone in possession of a decoding key. Additionally, we agreed that if the key file (i.e. additional information to attribute personal data to the data subject) has been preserved in any way, the data is considered pseudonymous, even if the data user has no means to obtain or access the key file. Note that this interpretation is currently under debate and a case in the European Court challenges this. However, as this is a strict interpretation it should meet the requirements of less stringent interpretations as well. It is also important to realize that datasets may contain so called natural keys. Natural keys are (combinations of) variables that can be used to construct a unique identifier for a data subject. In essence, natural keys are a pseudonym. Commonly used natural keys are composite keys that may be the combination of variables such as sex, age, and other date-time variables. In health data diagnoses or treatments can be natural keys as well. The richer the data, the more likely a natural key can be constructed. This is one of the main reasons that data minimization is such an important aspect of data protection.

4.1.3. Anonymized data

Anonymous data is defined as information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person and cannot be traced to an individual's identity by any means. This means that there are no primary keys in the data, no pseudonyms, natural keys, nor composite keys that may be used to re-identify a person. In order to ensure that data is truly anonymous, dataset of anonymous data tend to be very minimalized to ensure that no composite keys can be constructed. This also severely limits the utility of anonymous data.

4.1.4. Synthetic data

Synthetic data is annotated information that computer simulations or algorithms generate as an alternative to real-world data. The concept of synthetic data generation is to take an original data source (dataset) and create new, artificial data with similar statistical properties from it without memorizing original data. Thus, synthetic data aims to combine the strong data protection that anonymous data offers, with the utility and richness that pseudonymised data provides. The creation of synthetic data entails a machine learning algorithm that is used to infer distributions and associations between variables from a dataset. This is in essence an aggregation process. For example, one can determine the mean age and the standard deviation of age from a population of patients. These are then parameters to a distribution that can be sampled through simulation to create a new dataset with that mean and standard deviation of age. The model is subsequently used to generate new data from the distributions that were learned from the training data, resulting a set of simulated patient level data. In that respect, the data is similar to anonymous data, as the data is at the personal level, but not directly related to any real patient.

4.1.5. Aggregated data

Aggregated data is defined as data that is derived from personal data through aggregation procedures, such as counting, calculating proportions and measures of central tendency and dispersion of the data, for example mean and standard deviation, provided that the

procedures were performed on a sufficiently large sample. The larger the sample, the lower the identification risk

4.2. Current state of data access procedures

The next section gives a high-level overview of current data access procedures of PHEMS data controllers.

Through a series of workshops, the data controllers (HUS, HSJD, GOSH, Erasmus MC, Meyer, and BKUS) generated a set of user journey maps for data access and transfer. We differentiated between pseudonymous data, generally used for research, and anonymous data, often used for quality control and benchmarking. While maturity of the processes varied between the data controllers, the following common steps were identified:

1. Data discovery by the data user.
2. Registration of the data request by the data user.
3. Approval of the data request by the data controller.
4. Data preparation by the data processor (usually also the controller).
5. Provisioning of a secure processing environment by the data processor.
6. Release of the data by the data provider to the data user.

Data discovery – Only HUS offers a public facing meta data catalogue. Other organizations are either in the process of acquiring a catalogue (Erasmus MC) or rely on informal networks of researchers for data access (Erasmus MC, GOSH, HSJD, Meyer, and BKUS).

Registration of the data request – This step is the initiation of data access for all centres. HUS has a platform where external users can register and request a quote for data access. Other centres require a contact from their institution to be part of a collaborative data project. All centres require the data user to submit a project plan and a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) that includes the processing base for data use as well as data transfer agreements if data leaves the controller. Some centres also require a Data Management Plan.

Approval of the data request – Once the required documentation is created and submitted by the data user, some form of review takes place in all centres. In some cases, the review is mostly administrative with the possibility to escalate to expert reviews, such as a research ethics committee or data protection officer (DPO). In other cases, the DPO or a mandated data protection team reviews the application in detail. This process is largely manual in all centres and functions on a case-by-case basis.

Data preparation – If a data request is approved, the specifications of the request are passed to a data team tasked with Extracting, Transforming and Loading (ETL) the data from the hospital data warehouse and generating the requested dataset. In all hospitals this was still a semi-automated task at best with engineers writing queries for separate data requests. GOSH worked with standardized datasets to streamline the work. None of the centres has self-service query tools in place.

Provisioning of a secure processing environment – HUS, GOSH and Erasmus MC offer secure processing environments to data users for data processing. This means that in some cases, the data does not even leave control of the hospital. The process to request an SPE was fairly similar for all three centres, and was performed by a third part service provider. The other centres did not have SPEs or were in the process of acquiring a SPE service provider.

Release of the data – With the data prepared and a secure processing environment in place, data is uploaded where it may be accessed by the data user.

In summary, all participating hospitals have some form of procedure at various levels of maturity to handle data access requests as well as the infrastructure to provide data access. While the detailed steps varied between the participants, the general process was similar across hospitals and aligned well with the generic EHDS process described below.

4.3. Target Data Access Process for PHEMS ecosystem

The next section describes a general overview of the envisioned PHEMS data access procedure. The procedure was created through a series of workshops where the ecosystem parties described existing procedures and policies for data access at their institutions in relation to national laws and European regulations. Compared to the generic EHDS data access approval process,(2) an additional data collection step has been added and a few steps have been broken down into smaller tasks. This was done to add clarity and isolate components in the process so that the data provider can easily abstract and implement using their own systems and existing processes.

4.3.1. Roles

We describe the following roles following the definitions from the Open DEI Design Principles for Data Spaces whitepaper (<https://design-principles-for-data-spaces.org/>):

Open DEI definitions	PHEMS definition
Data consumers: they access data spaces to use data.	Data user is person or organization that is authorized to exploit the data.
Data provider: they collect and manage data and make it available in data spaces.	Data Processor is a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the data controller.
Data producers: they create data.	Data controller: they are the data controller in the way GDPR defines them: a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data
Data owners: they have rights to grant or revoke terms and conditions for access and use of data.	

Note that the **data controller** and **data processor** may be the same legal entity. In the text below **data processor** may refer to one or multiple entities that operate on behalf of the data controller.

4.3.2. Process descriptions

In the following chapters, the actions, decisions, and processes performed by the roles are described by color codes and symbol as shown in figure below.

Figure 1. Legend to the data access process maps.

4.3.3. Preliminary Step: Data Collection

This step is preliminary, and not directly in scope of PHEMS. The aim of this step is to create a scalable process that allows data controllers to provide high quality data to data users in a timely and cost-efficient manner. By principle PHEMS will adhere to the common data standards in health: OMOP CDM and DCAT-AP when exchanging data & meta data. The former largely applies to health data research, while the latter is a widely accepted meta data standard that is set to be extended specifically for health data by 2024.(3, 4)

Figure 2. Data collection by the data controller prior to the data access process initiation.

Prerequisites

- The data controller has a solution to:
 - extract data from sources,
 - transform that data to the OMOP Common Data Model,
 - and load data into storage
- The data controller can host a meta data catalogue.

Inputs

- Data that is stored in data management systems, e.g. a hospital data warehouse, in support of the provision and management of clinical care.
- Data that is stored in data management systems in support of scientific research with human subjects, e.g. a clinical trial database.

Process

1. Data is collected either in support of the healthcare process or for research purposes and stored in a data management system, such as an EHR or research databases.
2. Data is extracted from source systems, such as EHR, laboratory information systems, and research databases, and loaded into a storage facility. The storage facility may be for example a data warehouse, data lake, or data lakehouse.
3. The data is made ready for secondary use by passing it through an Extraction-Transform-Load (ETL) pipeline to:
 - a. Pseudonymise the data
 - b. Map the data to a common data model the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) and associated vocabularies (e.g. SNOMED-CT, ICD10, LOINC, etc.), to promote interoperability and reusability of the data.
4. The data is preserved in long-term storage, either on-premises, in a private cloud, or a virtual private cloud.
5. Meta data is published for access through a meta data portal.

Outputs

- Health data that is modelled according to the OMOP CDM.
- Meta data that is modelled according DCAT.

4.3.4. Step 1: Data discovery

The aim of this step is to allow data users to discover data that can support their use cases, such as scientific research or quality benchmarking. Data discovery is split into two subprocesses: broad data discovery through a public meta data catalogue with a low trust process that helps data users screen for potentially useful data; and refined data discovery through a restricted meta data catalogue with more detail and functionality, and a trust process that will allow a data user to select a cohort of data subjects.

Figure 3. Data discovery process, broad search with public meta data for low trust context.

4.3.4.1. Broad search

The aim of the broad search is to assess feasibility of data use, and discover if data required for research exists.

Prerequisites

- Meta data catalogue according to DCAT standard.

Inputs

- Meta data according to DCAT standard.
- Query by data user

Process

1. **Data user** browses to a public portal to gain access to meta data catalogue.
2. The **data user** builds a query through form-based input.
3. The **data user** promotes the query to the meta data catalogue which executes the query and returns meta data, for example the time period, the geographical region, and overall population to which the data pertains.

In addition, the query returns aggregated data such as the datasets that are available, what variables are available and the total number of observations in the dataset. The result must contain only aggregated data, and no data at the data subject level, classified data, nor tooling to select and filter to create subsets of the data, so it can be accessed freely without any registration.

Outputs

- High level report of available datasets:
 - Meta data about the dataset according to DCAT
 - What variables (features) are available
 - Total number of observations per dataset

Figure 4. Data discovery, refined search for medium trust context.

4.3.4.2. Refined search

The aim of the refined search is to discover datasets with specific cohort requirements.

Prerequisites

- The data user is identifiable through eIDAS.
- The data user is associated with a trusted organization.
- The data user is registered through a portal (the PHEMS portal).

Input

- Meta data according to DCAT standard.
- Query by data user

Process

1. The **data user** logs into the restricted access section of the meta data catalogue.
2. The **data user** is shown additional features that allow the user to filter and select data from the meta data catalogue.
3. The **data user** builds a query through form-based input with the additional filtering and selection options.
4. The query is sent to the meta data catalogue which executes the query and returns descriptions of one or more detailed datasets.

5. The **data user** reviews the descriptions of the datasets, such as variable names, number of observations, and summary statistics per variable.
6. The **data user** saves the query that they used to select their datasets.
7. The **data user** requests a quote for data access from the data providers and controllers.
8. The data user is pointed to the Data Permit application step.

Outputs

- High level report of the requested dataset.
- Query to build the requested dataset
- Quotes for data access and SPE

4.3.5. Step 2: Data Permit application

The aim of the Data Permit application step is to ensure that use of the data is according to the terms and conditions for data access and use set by the data controller, so that the data controller can fulfil their obligation to protect the data subject's personal data.

Figure 5. Data permit application.

Prerequisites

- Data user has received a quote from the data controller and/or data processor.
- Data user has created a query from the meta data catalogue application.
- Data user has logged into the PHEMS portal.
- Data controller has a Data Access Committee in place with possibility to escalate questions and issues to topic experts (legal, ethical, data protection, cybersecurity) if needed.
- Data controller has an established appeal process for the data permit application.

Process

1. The data user creates an entry in a GPDR processing registry describing:
 - to which data subjects the processing pertains (*i.e.* what cohort),
 - the purpose of the data use,
 - what data is being processed, and
 - on what legal basis.
2. The data user submits a Data Management Plan (DMP) that details the responsible persons and their roles in the project and how the data user will comply with the FAIR principles.
3. The data user also creates a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) describing organization and technical measures taken to mitigate data protection risks.
4. The data user signs a Data Access Agreement (DAA) or Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) that covers terms and conditions that have not been addressed by the DMP and DPIA.
5. The data user fills out the Data Permit application form. The form also includes the DAA or DTA, DMP and DPIA as annexes.
6. The data user submits the Data Permit application form for administrative review.
7. The data controller performs the administrative review.
8. The data controller notifies the data user of the decision.
 - a. If the data permit is denied, the data user will be notified and informed about the reasons for the rejection of the request.
 - b. If the data permit is approved, the data user is issued a data access permit.

Outputs

- Data Permit application
- Data Permit decision
- Data Permit decision notification
- Data Permit

4.3.6. Step 3: Data access application

The aim of this step is to ensure that a verified, minimized set of high quality data is delivered to the data user, so that the data controller can fulfil their data protection obligations to the data subject, and that the data user has access to the data that they need for the processing purpose.

Figure 6. Data access process.

Prerequisites

- The data user has obtained a data permit
- The data user has reserved a SPE.

Input

- Data Permit
- Reference to cohort specifications

- Reference to project

Process

1. The data user submits their data permit
2. The data processor validates the data permit.
3. The data processor retrieves the data specifications from the source code management system utilized in Cohort selection in Step 1a Refined Search.
4. The data processor validates the query against the data permit.
5. The data processor runs the query against storage to retrieve the requested data.
6. The data processor takes additional de-identification steps, either anonymization, synthetization, or double pseudonymisation if required by the data permit.
7. The data processor registers the resulting dataset in the meta data catalogue.
8. The data processor publishes the dataset for upload to the SPE.

Output

- Dataset
- Metadata for dataset
- Notification to data user

4.3.7. Step 4: Data provision

The aim of this step is to ensure that data is shared or accessed through a secure processing environment so that the data controller can fulfil their obligation to the data subject and ensure data protection.

Figure 7. Secure Processing Environment application process.

Prerequisites

- The data user has obtained a data permit
- The data user has logged in through the PHEMS portal

Input

- Data permit

Process

1. The data user can request an SPE through the PHEMS portal.
2. The data user submits their data permit.
3. The submitted data permit is validated by the data processor.
4. The data user provides administrative information required for billing
5. The data processor reserves an SPE for the data user.

Output

- Secure processing environment

4.3.8. Step 5: Data use

The aim of this step is to use the data within the terms and conditions of use. The data processor will monitor resource consumption for billing purposes. The data controller will monitor access logs to ensure compliance with terms and conditions as well compliance with legal requirements.

Figure 8. Data use.

Prerequisites

- The data user has a valid data permit.
- The data user has requested a SPE.
- The data provider has reserved a SPE for the data user.

- The data provider has retrieved the requested data.

Process

1. The data processor retrieves the dataset from storage and uploads it to the SPE.
2. The data processor verifies that de-identification measures have been implemented.
3. The data processor assigns roles and permissions defined according to the data permit to the data user
4. The data controller verifies the roles, permissions, and data access through access logs.
5. The data processor gives the data users access to the SPE.
6. The data processor continues to monitor usage logs for billing.
7. The data processor monitors security logs for cybersecurity incident response and mitigation purposes.
8. The data processor sends periodic invoices, based on resource consumption and the Terms of Use to the data user.

4.4. Processing bases for PHEMS ecosystem partners

The next table gives an overview of the legal processing bases that are generally accepted across the PHEMS ecosystem. The main purpose is to give data users and data controller a starting point for future discussion to help harmonize data access procedures as well as the drafting of template DAAs and DTAs.

Country	Data Type		
	Directly identifying	Pseudonymous	Anonymous
Finland	Data must be pseudonymised before reuse unless this is impossible or requires disproportionate efforts.	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained <i>OR</i> it is in the public interest . Findata is responsible for the review and issuance of data permits. Data must be analysed in a Secure Processing Environment	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if informed consent has been obtained, to meet a legal obligation, <i>OR</i> it is in the public interest . Findata is responsible for the review and issuance of data permits. Data must be analysed in a Secure Processing Environment
Italy		Reuse of personal health data is only permitted if the data subject has provided express, separate written specific informed consent .	Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j.
Latvia	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if: specific informed consent has been obtained <i>OR</i> Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j.	

Country	Data Type		
	Directly identifying	Pseudonymous	Anonymous
Spain		<p>The reuse of personal health data is permitted if there is broad informed consent as detailed below:</p> <p>The Additional 17th Provision of the Organic Law 3/2018 implies that reuse of personal data for health and biomedical research purposes is considered lawful provided that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prior informed consent of the study was given and that the reuse is for purposes or areas related to the initial purpose for which informed consent was given. • The data user gives information about use on their website to comply with GDPR Art 13 <p>A prior favourable opinion from an ethics committee has been obtained</p>	
The Netherlands		<p>Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained. In some situations, consent may be waived when requesting consent is impossible or requires disproportionate effort. This proportionality needs to be assessed on a case-by-case basis to determine if special legal processing bases apply.</p>	<p>Health data collected for medical treatment may be used in anonymized form if the data subject has not objected to such use.</p>
United Kingdom		<p>Personal health data may be reused without consent if processing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is necessary for scientific research • Is carried out in accordance with F4UK GPDR 89(1). • Is in the public interest. <p>Data subject may opt out of secondary use.</p>	

To the best of our knowledge there is no clear processing base for synthetic data. However, from a technical and data protection risk point of view synthetic data sits somewhere between pseudonymous and aggregated data. In essence, it may be viewed as an aggregation technique to simulate data. In terms of risk of re-identification, it appears similar to anonymous data. While not fully impossible to determine if a person was part of the

training data set, the effort and technical complexity to re-identify a data subject is far greater than for pseudonymous data. Workpackage 3 is tasked with providing metrics for this re-identification risk as well as implementing a framework to assess re-identification risk, so that data controllers can make a well founded decision to provide either anonymous, synthetic or pseudonymous data for a given data request.

4.5. Monitoring and evaluation recommendations

In order to measure the impact of the harmonized data access procedures we that PHEMS may set up a continuous monitoring system to track the following key performance indicators (KPIs):

- The number of sessions and unique users for the data discovery services.
- Lead time from data discovery to release of the data for data use in days.
- Cycle time for transition to each following step in the procedure in days.
 - Data discovery to data permit application.
 - Data permit application to data access application.
 - Data access application to release of data for data use.
- The number and percentages for approved and abandoned data permits per year.
- The number and utilisation of secure processing environments.

In addition to the monitoring system, we suggest to perform a baseline measurement by determining the above KPIs for demonstration projects described in work package 4 tasks 2, 3 and 4.

4.6. Suggested follow-up actions

The target data access procedures described in this document aim to harmonize and streamline the data access requests across the ecosystem. The intended result is to enable generating feedback on data permits and data application request more quickly, thus decreasing the time from data discovery to data use.

An extension to harmonizing the data access procedures may be a harmonized process to generate data permits and terms-of-use for the data. Data permits and terms-of-use need to be flexible to account for differences in processing bases across EU member states, but streamlined to more quickly construct the data access permits and reduce administrative burden on data controllers and menial tasks for privacy lawyers. Below we suggest an initial set of principles and user requirements from discussions with the teams at the participating organizations. These may serve as inspiration for the development of a possible service to broker data permits.

4.6.1. Principles for harmonization of data access agreements and data transfer agreements

- Design from the data user and data provider perspectives.

- Responsibility and accountability for the data access and data transfer agreements lies at the bilateral level between data provider and data user. A central governance body ensures compliance with general principles for the ecosystem through audits.
- Components need clear ownership.
- All components comply with European law.
- Specific implementations of a component need to comply with the national law(s) of the data controller.

4.6.2. Functional requirements

- As a data controller I want base images (or versions) of modules of agreements to adhere to FAIR principles and thus be readable to both humans and machines, so that I can easily choose the modules that are suitable for my use case.
- As a data controller I want base images of modules to follow standardized templates, so that I can easily browse through them to find relevant information.
- As a data controller I want to have a streamlined, preferably automated, process to generate the documents from the components so that I can reduce menial tasks as much as possible.
- As a developer I want components that can be refined to meet national and institutional policies as forks or branches of the centralized agreements.
- As a privacy lawyer I want a way to easily compare, contrast and resolve differences between implementations of a module of an agreement.
- As an end user I want a Graphical User Interface that aids me with the review through search, find, and highlighting functionalities so that I can quickly compare differences between texts.
- As an auditor, I want documentation about the process through which agreements were constructed that clearly explains the roles and responsibilities of those involved during the agreement process.
- As a privacy lawyer I want modules of the agreements to be loosely coupled so that an overall agreement can be constructed by picking and choosing components that are required for a specific use case.
- As a data controller I want components to be Open Access and reusable under a permissive license, so that I can easily share these with data users.

5. Conclusions

The current data access process for PHEMS participants is varied in maturity. General steps for data access procedures were identified through workshops and include data

discovery, request registration, approval by data controllers, data preparation, and secure data release.

The envisioned PHEMS data access procedure aims to align with European Health Data Space (EHDS) framework, enhancing clarity and component isolation for easy implementation. It includes detailed roles and responsibilities, data collection standards, and a step-by-step data access process.

Processing bases for different data types across EU member states differ with regards to pseudonymized data. Anonymous and synthetic data are not considered personal data and therefore are out of scope of GDPR, highlighting the value of federated and synthetic data.

Implementation of a monitoring and evaluation plan is crucial to assess the performance and impact of the data access process. This includes defining KPIs, methods, and tools for continuous improvement and ensuring the success of the PHEMS project in pediatric healthcare.

6. References

1. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), (2016).
2. Team THDE. Report of the European Commission webinars on the European Health Data Spaces (EHDS) for secondary use of health data for research purposes. Brussels: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Unit D.2 Health Innovations & Ecosystems; 2023.
3. Celia Alvarez-Romero AM-G. Guidelines to standardise metadata templates and assessment of FAIRness maturity levels. Sevilla Servicio Andaluz de Salud; 2022.
4. Pilot HE. Extension of DCAT-AP: HealthDCAT-AP: EHDS HealthyData@EU Pilot; 2024 [Available from: https://ehds2pilot.eu/upcoming_results/extension-of-dcat-ap-healthdcat-ap/].
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6. Johan Hansen PW, Eline Verhoeven, Madelon Kroneman, Mary Kirwan, Robert Verheij, Evert-Ben van Veen. Assessment of the EU Member States' rules on health data in the light of GDPR. Luxembourg: Publications office of the European Union; 2021.

7. Appendix

The following table was adapted from Health-RI and NIVEL.(5, 6)

Country	Data Type		
	Directly identifying	Pseudonymous	Anonymous
Austria	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained. <i>OR</i> Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j.	
Bulgaria		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Belgium		Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained. <i>OR</i> Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j <i>OR</i> In some situations consent may be waived when requesting consent is impossible or requires disproportionate effort.	
Croatia		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research. Approval by an ethics committee is required.	
Cyprus		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Czech Republic		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Denmark		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research with the exception of genetic data. Approval by an ethics committee is required.	
Estonia	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained. In some situations consent may be waived .	Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j

Country	Data Type		
	Directly identifying	Pseudonymous	Anonymous
Finland	Data must be pseudonymised before reuse unless this is impossible or requires disproportionate efforts.	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained <i>OR</i> it is in the public interest . Findata is responsible for the review and issuance of data permits. Data must be analysed in a Secure Processing Environment	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if informed consent has been obtained, to meet a legal obligation, <i>OR</i> it is in the public interest . Findata is responsible for the review and issuance of data permits. Data must be analysed in a Secure Processing Environment
France		Reuse of personal health data is permitted (GDPR Art 9.2.j) for research unless the data subject has opted out . The data user still needs to comply with GDPR Art 12-23 and request approval for reuse at the Commission National de l'Informatique des Libertes (CNIL).	
Germany		Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained (with the exception of cancer registries and claims data). <i>OR</i> Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j <i>OR</i> In some situations consent may be waived when requesting consent is impossible or requires disproportionate effort.	
Greece		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Hungary		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research. Approval by the Data Protection Officer (DPO) or director of the data controller as well as approval by an ethics committee is required.	
Ireland	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained	Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j. Approval by an ethics committee is required.	
Italy		Reuse of personal health data is only permitted if the data subject has provided express, separate written specific informed consent .	Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j.

Country	Data Type		
	Directly identifying	Pseudonymous	Anonymous
Latvia	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if: specific informed consent has been obtained OR Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j.	
Lithuania		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Luxembourg		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research with the exception of genetic data. Approval by an ethics committee is required.	
Malta	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained	Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained OR Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j.	
Poland		Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained OR Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j	Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research.
Portugal		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Romania		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	

Country	Data Type		
	Directly identifying	Pseudonymous	Anonymous
Spain		<p>The reuse of personal health data is permitted if there is broad informed consent as detailed below:</p> <p>The Additional 17th Provision of the Organic Law 3/2018 implies that reuse of personal data for health and biomedical research purposes is considered lawful provided that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prior informed consent of the study was given and that the reuse is for purposes or areas related to the initial purpose for which informed consent was given. • The data user gives information about use on their website to comply with GDPR Art 13 • A prior favourable opinion from an ethics committee has been obtained 	
Slovenia		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Slovakia		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
Sweden		Reuse of personal health data is permitted for scientific research under GDPR Art 9.2.j – there is no specific legislation in this member state.	
The Netherlands		<p>Reuse of personal health data is permitted if specific informed consent has been obtained.</p> <p>In some situations, consent may be waived when requesting consent is impossible or requires disproportionate effort. This proportionality needs to be assessed on a case-by-case basis to determine if special legal processing bases apply.</p>	Health data collected for medical treatment may be used in anonymized form if the data subject has not objected to such use.
United Kingdom		<p>Personal health data may be reused without consent if processing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is necessary for scientific research • Is carried out in accordance with F4UK GPDR 89(1). • Is in the public interest. <p>Data subject may opt out of secondary use.</p>	

